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BARRIERS AND BRIDGES: AI FOR CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AND CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION AT A NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The perception of lecturers, students and administrators regarding the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing classroom effectiveness and the institutional and technological barriers to AI implementation was determined in this research. A survey design was adopted, using a questionnaire to collect quantitative and qualitative data from 225 participants, including lecturers, students, and ICT staff. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that large class sizes, inadequate teaching resources, student disengagement, and limited use of technology significantly impede effective curriculum delivery. Respondents generally perceived AI as a valuable tool for lesson planning, student assessment, interactive learning, and administrative support, but its adoption was hindered by limited access to AI tools, inadequate ICT infrastructure, lack of training, resistance to change, and budget constraints. The study concludes that AI has the potential to improve classroom management and curriculum delivery, provided there is institutional support, adequate infrastructure, and capacity-building initiatives. Recommendations include deploying AI tools, providing professional development, and investing in ICT infrastructure to enhance teaching and learning outcomes.

Keywords: AI, Classroom Management, Curriculum, Implementation, University.

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INTRODUCTION

Classroom management is a critical component of effective teaching and learning, especially within higher education institutions where diverse learner needs, complex curricula, and limited resources often create significant challenges. In Nigeria, universities such as the Federal University of Education, Zaria, face ongoing difficulties in delivering quality education. These include large class sizes, limited teacher-student interaction, low engagement levels, and a mismatch between curriculum content and implementation strategies (Okoye & Nwafor, 2022). Traditional classroom management techniques, though valuable, often fall short in addressing these issues within the context of modern education. AI has emerged globally as a disruptive force in the education sector, offering tools that can automate, personalise, and enhance the learning experience. AI can improve classroom management through systems such as facial recognition for attendance, automated lesson planning, real-time behavioural analysis, adaptive learning platforms, and intelligent tutoring systems

(Chen et al., 2020). These technologies help educators better manage time, student behaviour, and instructional effectiveness. Globally, countries like China, the United States, and Finland are leading in educational AI adoption, showcasing improvements in classroom efficiency and learning outcomes (Holmes et al., 2019).

In contrast, the application of AI in many African educational institutions remains in its infancy. In Nigeria, despite policy emphasis on digital transformation, issues such as poor internet infrastructure, limited digital literacy, lack of training, and ethical concerns about surveillance and privacy hinder AI's adoption in teaching and learning (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020). Nevertheless, integrating AI into classroom management is essential for aligning Nigerian universities with global trends and for supporting the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4: quality education for all. Classroom management extends beyond enforcing discipline to include effective time management, addressing behavioural concerns, sustaining student motivation, and ensuring that

instructional delivery aligns with curriculum objectives. When these elements are poorly managed, curriculum implementation is weakened, resulting in student disengagement and reduced academic performance (Holmes et al., 2019). AI can enhance this by automating repetitive tasks, providing real-time data on student engagement, and supporting inclusive teaching strategies (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). In doing so, it allows teachers to focus more on pedagogy and student-centred learning.

Curriculum implementation in teacher education institutions like the Federal University of Education, Zaria, translates designed content into practice via teaching and learning activities, relying on competent delivery, learner engagement, and institutional support. Yet many of them face challenges like overcrowded classrooms, delayed assessments, and a lack of personalisation. Integrating AI into classroom management addresses these bottlenecks by enhancing efficiency and outcomes (Okoye & Nwafor, 2022), aligning with UN SDG 4 for inclusive, equitable education through personalised learning, expanded resources, data-driven decisions, and early gap identification to reduce waste, especially in low-resource Nigerian contexts (UNESCO, 2021). The TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006) underpins this by integrating technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge, ensuring AI tools like monitoring systems align with curriculum goals to boost participation and feedback rather than mere automation. This paper focuses on how AI tools can be applied to support classroom management and enhance curriculum implementation at the Federal University of Education, Zaria. It investigates existing challenges, stakeholder perceptions, and barriers to AI adoption.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) has transformed educational practices globally, offering new tools for classroom management, personalised learning, and curriculum implementation. However, in Nigerian universities of education, the integration of AI into teaching

and learning remains limited, and significant challenges persist. Lecturers continue to struggle with managing large class sizes, maintaining student engagement, and providing timely feedback, while students experience delays in assessment results and limited personalised learning opportunities. Although AI has the potential to automate administrative tasks, support real-time monitoring, and enhance pedagogical practices, many institutions lack the necessary infrastructure, technical expertise, and awareness to fully leverage these technologies. Furthermore, the adoption of AI is hindered by inadequate ICT facilities, budget constraints, resistance to change, and insufficient training for academic and administrative staff. These barriers compromise the effective implementation of curriculum objectives and reduce the quality of teaching and learning. While AI has proven benefits in educational contexts elsewhere, its potential in Nigerian universities remains largely untapped, creating a gap between technological possibilities and practical application. This study seeks to identify the barriers that limit AI adoption and the potential bridges, such as training, infrastructure development, and policy support, that can enhance AI integration for classroom management and curriculum implementation. Understanding these factors is critical to developing strategies that can improve teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and the overall quality of education in Nigerian universities of education.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. identify the major classroom management challenges affecting curriculum delivery at FUE, Zaria.
2. determine the perception of lecturers, students, and ICT administrators regarding the role of Artificial Intelligence in improving classroom effectiveness.
3. investigate the institutional and technological barriers hindering the implementation of AI for curriculum support in FCE Zaria.

Research Questions

The research questions raised to guide this study are:

1. What are the major classroom management challenges affecting curriculum delivery at FUE, Zaria?
2. How do lecturers, students, and ICT administrators perceive AI's role in improving classroom effectiveness?
3. What institutional and technological barriers exist in implementing AI for curriculum support?

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a Survey design to explore the application of AI in classroom management for improving curriculum implementation at the Federal University of Education, Zaria. The combination of both quantitative and qualitative research methods allows for a comprehensive analysis of stakeholders' perceptions, institutional practices, and contextual challenges. The total population size of the study is 550, consisting of 250 lecturers from education, 250 students, and 50 ICT staff and administrators within the Faculty of Education, Federal University of Education, Zaria. Specifically, this included: All teaching staff across the education departments, all undergraduate students enrolled in the Faculty of Education and all personnel responsible for IT support and technological infrastructure in the faculty. From this population of 550, using the table of Krejcie & Morgan (1970), 225 was adopted as the sample. The sample was selected using purposive sampling, targeting participants with prior experience or exposure to classroom management and technology use. The final sample included: 100 lecturers from various education departments; 100 undergraduate students, and 25 ICT officers and administrators. This sampling strategy ensured that the study captured relevant perspectives on classroom management challenges and the application of AI in curriculum delivery.

To ensure validity, questionnaire items were reviewed by three educational technology and curriculum experts for clarity and relevance. Reliability was confirmed through a pilot test, which yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.84, indicating internal consistency. Data for this study were collected using a combination of

questionnaires and interviews, in line with the survey design adopted. Structured questionnaires were administered to lecturers and students to gather quantitative data on classroom management challenges, perceptions of AI in teaching, and experiences with technological tools, using 5 Likert scales for measurable responses. Data were collected simultaneously from all participant groups, with questionnaires distributed in person and electronically, while interviews were scheduled at convenient times for participants. This approach, according to Chen et al. (2020), enabled a comprehensive understanding of classroom management practices and the perceived role of AI in enhancing teaching and learning. Data collected from questionnaires and interviews were analysed using both quantitative and qualitative techniques. Quantitative data from closed-ended questionnaire items were coded and input to SPSS for statistical analysis, including descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations to summarise respondents' views on classroom management challenges and AI usage.

RESULTS

The results are organised according to the research questions to provide a logical presentation of the findings as follows:

Table 1: Classroom Management Challenges as Perceived by Respondents (N = 225)

Challenge	Lecturers mean	Students mean	ICT/Admin mean	Cumulative Mean	SD	Decision
Large class sizes	4.89	4.78	4.00	4.57	10.4	Agree
Inadequate teaching resources	4.66	4.33	4.00	4.33	5.00	Agree
Student disengagement	4.00	4.35	3.33	3.89	10.0	Agree
Limited use of technology	3.67	4.00	4.67	4.11	7.64	Agree
Classroom disruptions	3.33	3.67	2.67	3.22	7.64	Agree

The analysis of responses from lecturers, students, and ICT/administrative staff reveals that large class sizes pose the most significant challenge to effective classroom management, with a cumulative mean of 4.57 and a standard deviation of 10.41. Lastly, classroom disruptions recorded the lowest mean score = 3.22 and SD = 7.64, suggesting it is less critical compared to other challenges, though still relevant. Overall, the findings show resource and structural challenges are

more pressing than behavioural ones, highlighting the need for investment in facilities and capacity building in technology integration.

Table 2: Perception of AI in Classroom Effectiveness (N = 225)

Aspect of AI Use	Cumulative Mean	SD	Decision
Lesson planning support	4.81	5.0	Agree
Student assessment & feedback	4.78	7.6	Agree
Interactive learning & engagement	4.89	5.0	Agree
Automation of administrative tasks	4.78	15.3	Agree

Table 2 presents the results of the cumulative mean and standard deviation. The analysis indicates that respondents across the three groups generally agree that AI plays a significant role in educational tasks. Lesson planning support and interactive learning recorded strong agreement among respondents, each with a cumulative mean of 4.81 and 4.89, respectively, suggesting the perception that AI tools are valuable for preparing learning content and enhancing student engagement.

Table 3: Barriers to AI Integration (N = 225)

Barrier	Lecturers	Students	ICT/Admin	Overall	Overall	Decision
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	SD	
Limited access to AI tools	4.67	4.33	4.89	4.63	7.64	Agree
Inadequate infrastructure	4.00	3.67	4.91	4.19	12.74	Agree
Lack of technical training	4.89	4.00	4.87	4.59	8.50	Agree
Resistance to change among staff	4.67	3.33	4.00	4.00	6.24	Agree
Budget constraints	4.00	3.67	4.66	4.11	6.24	Agree
Cumulative Mean (per respondent)	4.45	3.00	4.67			

The results indicate significant disparities in perceived barriers to AI integration among the three respondent groups. ICT and administrative staff reported the highest overall challenge level (mean = 4.67), reflecting their direct responsibility for system deployment, maintenance, and infrastructure support. Students presented the lowest perceived barrier (mean = 3.00), which may suggest limited involvement in institutional decisions and infrastructural realities, hence a lower awareness of the underlying challenges. Overall, the findings reveal that successful adoption of AI in higher education requires a holistic approach that combines infrastructure upgrades, capacity building, and organisational change management.

DISCUSSION

The study findings highlight several key barriers to effective AI integration and classroom management in higher education, corroborated by both quantitative survey data and qualitative interviews with lecturers, students, and ICT personnel. The analysis of classroom management challenges in Table 1 shows strong agreement among lecturers, students, and ICT/administrative staff that large class sizes, inadequate teaching resources, student disengagement, limited use of technology, and classroom disruptions significantly hinder effective teaching and learning. Large class sizes posed the greatest challenge, consistent with previous research highlighting their negative impact on instructional quality and learner interaction. Inadequate teaching resources and limited technology use further reinforce long-standing concerns about resource constraints in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Student disengagement also remains a substantial issue, influenced by motivation, learning conditions, and institutional factors. Although classroom disruptions were perceived as less severe compared to other challenges, they still represent a notable concern. Overall, the findings reveal systemic and interconnected challenges that require comprehensive institutional reforms, including improved resource provision, enhanced digital infrastructure, and strategies aimed at boosting student engagement. These results align with the broader literature, which identifies poor classroom management and inadequate technological support as major impediments to effective curriculum delivery in developing countries (Emmer & Evertson, 2016; Okoye & Nwafor, 2022).

The results in Table 2 show that respondents hold a strongly positive perception of the effectiveness of artificial intelligence in classroom-related functions. All four aspects of AI use recorded high cumulative mean scores, indicating broad agreement that AI can significantly enhance teaching and learning processes. Interactive learning and engagement received the highest mean score (4.89), suggesting that stakeholders view AI tools as highly effective in promoting active participation and improving learner interaction. Lesson planning support (4.81)

and student assessment and feedback (4.78) were also rated highly, reflecting confidence in AI's ability to streamline instructional preparation and provide timely, personalised feedback. Similarly, the use of AI to automate administrative tasks (4.78) was strongly supported, despite a relatively higher standard deviation, which may indicate varying levels of exposure or familiarity among respondents. Overall, the findings highlight widespread recognition of AI's potential to improve efficiency, enhance instructional quality, and support more engaging learning environments in line with Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019). These perceptions resonate with the TPACK framework, which suggests that effective integration occurs when educators understand how AI intersects with pedagogy and content (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Activity Theory further explains how AI tools can reshape interactions between teachers, students, and learning content, potentially enhancing engagement and instructional efficiency (Engeström, 1987).

The data in Table 3 reveal a strong consensus among lecturers, students, and ICT/administrative staff regarding key barriers to effective classroom integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies (Chukwuemeka & Okeke, 2025; Raymond, 2025). Limited access to AI tools (overall $M = 4.63$) and lack of technical training (overall $M = 4.59$) emerge as the most salient challenges, indicating that both resource availability and user competence substantially constrain meaningful adoption of AI for teaching and learning (Kalniņa et al. 2024). Inadequate ICT infrastructure (overall $M = 4.19$), reported most strongly by ICT/administrative staff, points to structural and systemic deficits (such as unreliable connectivity, obsolete hardware, and limited institutional platforms) that undermine the scalability of AI-driven solutions (Chukwuemeka & Okeke, 2025; Raymond, 2025). Organisational and human factors further complicate AI integration. Resistance to change among staff (overall $M = 4.00$) reflects concerns about workload, job security, and pedagogical disruption, which align with broader findings that scepticism and anxiety can slow AI adoption in higher

education (Kalniņa et al., 2024; Raymond, 2025). Budget constraints (overall $M = 4.11$) compound these challenges by limiting the ability of institutions to invest in AI tools, infrastructure upgrades, and sustained professional development programmes (Chukwuemeka & Okeke, 2025). Overall, the pattern of means and variability in

Table 3 highlights that successful AI adoption requires more than just technological availability. It requires deliberate capacity building for lecturers, students, and support staff, as well as clear institutional policies and governance frameworks, and adequate, sustained funding to address infrastructure gaps, training needs, and change management processes.

CONCLUSION

This study examined classroom management challenges, perceptions of AI's role in improving classroom effectiveness, and the barriers to AI integration in curriculum delivery at the Faculty of Education, FUE, Zaria. The findings revealed that large class sizes, inadequate teaching resources, student disengagement, limited use of technology, and classroom disruptions significantly affect curriculum delivery. Lecturers, students, and ICT staff generally perceive AI as a valuable tool for enhancing lesson planning, student assessment, interactive learning, and administrative tasks. However, institutional and technological barriers, including limited access to AI tools, inadequate ICT infrastructure, lack of training, resistance to change, and budget constraints, hinder its effective implementation. Overall, the study concludes that AI has the potential to significantly improve classroom management and curriculum delivery, but its adoption requires strategic planning, investment in infrastructure, and capacity building to ensure successful integration.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper recommends the following:

1. The Faculty of Education should implement AI-based tools and support systems, such as interactive learning systems, such as interactive learning platforms and automated classroom monitoring, to enhance lesson delivery, maintain student engagement, and reduce the impact of large class sizes.

2. Continuous professional development and training programs should be organised for lecturers, students, and administrative staff to build competence in AI applications and ensure these tools are effectively integrated into curriculum delivery.
3. The institution should invest in adequate ICT infrastructure, provide access to AI tools, and develop clear policies for AI adoption, ensuring sustainable and efficient integration into teaching, learning, and administrative processes.

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